

On The Newly Charged Particle

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Abstract

In this note we will investigate the possibility of three new charged particle, however we are not very sure whether it is composite or elementary and cast doubts about its being Fermions or Bosons. A new empirical formula to calculate the mass of atomic nucleus is also presented.

Keywords: Fermions, Baryon Number, Electroweak

Recently it was proposed [1] a method to describe the possibility of several new particles, we will here consider such rules to investigate other possible outcomes. This particle is speculative in nature.

Let us consider

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_1 & \varphi_2 \\ \varphi_4 & \varphi_3 \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

Four components with the rule

$$\varphi_1\varphi_3/e + (\varphi_2 - \varphi_4) = 0 \text{ rule 1}$$

Assume choices as shown

$$\varphi_1 = \text{charge of a particle of CHARGE} + 1e$$

$$\varphi_2 = \text{charge of a particle of charge} + 2e$$

$$\varphi_3 = \text{charge of any quark of charge} + 2/3e$$

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & +2 \\ \varphi_4 & +2/3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Simply calculating from rule 1 one can predict that a particle of charge +8/3 may exist.

Similarly a particle of charge five - third 5/3 and seven- third 7/3 might also exist. However it is a very preliminary investigation like other particle of charge fourth third recently speculated [2]. We have also developed a new formula to compute the mass of w boson (see ref [2]) which relates the mass of proton Higgs field VEV mass of photon and baryon number of quarks and in second formula it relates to bottom quark mass and Higgs boson mass. The well known equation to calculate the mass of atomic nuclei is

$$m = Zm_p + Nm_n - \frac{E_b}{c^2} \dots (a)$$

E_b is the binding energy, m_p is the mass of a proton, m_n is the mass of a neutron, Z is the number of protons and N is the number of neutrons. Assume natural unit $c=1$.

We investigated the problem to relate the Higgs VEV, weak vector charged boson (w boson) and the baryon number of quarks into our new mass calculating equation. It gives

$$m = -\frac{1}{2} \left[2 \left(\frac{E_b}{c^2} - Nm_n + m_p \right) - \frac{1}{2} M_b + Z(m_w + m_A - 3B^2\lambda) \right]$$

This formula is only and only approximate **and far from exact or accurate**. This formula holds good with respect to former formula (a) above mentioned **only when mass of proton is assumed as equal to mass of neutron i.e = 1 Gev=1000 MeV and** All values are approximate.

M_w is the mass of w boson approximately taken as =80000 MeV (80 GeV), λ is the Higgs field VEV (approximate)=246000 MeV (246 GeV), m_a is the mass of photon=0 MeV, B is the baryon number=1/3, M_b is the mass of the bottom quark approximately taken as 4000 MeV (4GeV). This formula is approximate to the former one in respect of computation. The primary attractive theme in this note is the particles which needs precise experimental outcomes to establish that it has any physical relevance.

Reference

- [1] Deep Jyoti Dutta. (2018). Dynamical Pattern of Elementary Particles. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1797603>
- [2] Deep Jyoti Dutta. (2018). On The Fractional Fundamental Boson. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2011637>

this is our best standard assumption for this formula to work according to former one. For approximate approximation we must put $m_p=938.27$ Mev and mass of neutron= 939.56 MeV which is far far from exact value compared to the former one (a).